

Expedition Report

2022 Mariana CORK-Lite Expedition to the Mariana Forearc

Ship: *R/V Kilo Moana*

ROV: *Jason*

Ports: Guam to Guam

As of 8/10/22

Load in Honolulu: 11/3/22

Leave Honolulu: 11/4/22

Arrive in Guam: 11/17/22

Leave Port for Operations: 11/20/22

Arrive Port End Operations: 12/17/22

Demobilize/Load Stores 12/18/22

Demobilize/Fuel: 12/19/22

Transit to Honolulu: 12/20/22-1/1/23

NSF Awarded Grants:

Collaborative Research: Characterization of Subduction Channel Processes, Borehole Sampling at Active Serpentinite Mud Volcanoes on the Mariana Forearc

1922671	Geoff Wheat	University of Alaska Fairbanks
1921361	Jeff Seewald	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
1921654	Susan Lang	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution

Collaborative Research: Volatile Sources and Sinks across the Mariana Forearc

2152551	Peter Barry	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
	Brandi Kiel Reese	University of South Alabama
	Karen Lloyd	University of Tennessee Knoxville

NASA Awarded Grant

NASA's Exobiology Program

80NSSC22K1631	Julie Huber	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
	Elizabeth Trembath-Reichert	Arizona State University

International Collaborators

Walter Menapace (Bremen), Achim Kopf, and Ken Takai (JAMSTEC)

Permits

Mariana Trench National Wildlife Refuge, U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service,
Department of the Interior Permit Number: **12541-22009**

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Summary of CORK Status Mariana Forearc

During the expedition three new CORK Lites were deployed in IODP Holes U1492D, U1496C, and U1497D. Each was similar; however, there were slight differences depending on the hole.

Each of the CORK-Lites included a standard stainless-steel ball valve (4" 316 1000 WOG), which was deployed in the half-opened position. These ball valves have a center clearance of 3.94 inches (10.08 cm). To open the ball valve, move the lever up into a vertical position by moving the handle in a counter clockwise motion. Note that there are pictures on the handle, but to close the ball valve move the handle in a clockwise direction until it is horizontal. Ball valves are seated in a plastic piece and can easily be removed by turning the valve counterclockwise. The entire top plug can be removed by using the pins and turning counterclockwise. The assembly was hand tightened. O-rings were used to seal the assembly to the cork body. O-

rings in the top seal assembly “dove tail” grooves are 2-375, 2-373, and 2-372. The assembly has an eye hook at the bottom so that it can be deployed with an instrument string that hangs below

in the casing and into the perforated casing. The CORK-Lites can be sampled by opening the ball valve and sampling discharging fluids or by lowering a sampling system through the ball valve and into the hole, or removing the ball valve or the top plug assembly and lowering samplers, and also through the sample ports.

Each of the Cork-Lites also has four Jannasch ports that accept a Jannasch handle (see drawings on page 24). Valves on the Jannasch port are opened by turning the valve clockwise into the vertical position with the o (open) at the top. Valves are closed by turning counterclockwise to the c (closed) in the horizontal position. There are two ½ inch ports and two other ports (typically one ¼ inch and one 1/8 inch; however, Hole U1497D has two ¼ inch ports). One of the ½ inch ports is dedicated to sampling, the other goes to the latches. Because of the overpressure at South Chamorro and the weight of the CORK-Lite was not heavy enough to counteract the potential overpressure, a latching system was installed. To release the latches, the valves need to be pressurized to 100 PSI. The other two ports are for sampling. You can see where the ports go into the CORK body and all ports are marked. Note that the ½ inch valve to the latches is marked “Keep Open”.

Hole U1496C Big Blue

The wellhead upon return had serpentinite mud in the reentry cone and there was no clear landing seat for the CORK-Lite to seal. When the CORK-Lite was deployed it didn't seat as designed, and thus didn't seal. Pressure data confirm hydrostatic condition in the CORK-Lite. Thus, seawater enters the top of the borehole below the CORK body and ascends with a mixture of formation fluid and seawater. The only means to get formation water is to lower an intake below the CORK body. The CORK body is about 18 feet (5.48 m) long. A 30-foot-long (9.14 m) inlet worked well to collect formation fluids. Note that the fluids have a high degree of white particles. For future dives, I suggest returning with an intake that is weighted to potentially break-up possibly brucite chimneys that may form in the space between the bottom of the CORK-Lite body and the top of the wellhead. The CORK-Lite was left with the ball valve closed, an RBR pressure sensor was left in the ¼ inch sample port with the valve opened, the latch valve remains open, and the other two sample valves were closed.

Hole U1467D Celestial

The CORK-Lite was seated in the wellhead as designed. With the ball valve opened it looked as though formation fluid (orangish color) was discharging from the wellhead. However, the pressure data show that the wellhead is at hydrostatic pressure (unless the ball valve leaked but there is no indication that it leaks) and the fluids that were collected are seawater with some iron oxide particles. The CORK-Lite was left with the ball valve closed, an RBR pressure sensor was

left in the ¼ inch sample port with the valve opened, the latch valve remains open, and the other two sample valves were closed.

Hole U1482D Blue Moon

The CORK-Lite was seated in the wellhead as designed. With the ball valve opened it looked as though formation fluid (whiteish color) was discharging from the wellhead and chemical data suggests that we collected a mixture of 20% formation fluid and 80% seawater. However, the pressure data show that the wellhead is at hydrostatic pressure (unless the ball valved leaked but there is no indication that it leaks), thus there is not a strong force related to discharge. Also, fluids that were collected have a slightly high pH than seawater, consistent with the mixtures listed above. The CORK-Lite was left with the ball valve closed, an RBR pressure sensor was left in the ¼ inch sample port with the valve opened, the latch valve remains open, and the other two sample valves were closed. Two sets of 32 pound dive weights were left on the ROV platform.

Hole 1200C South Chamorro

This hole has a history of development that is best summed up in the IODP Expedition 366 *Proceedings*. Currently the borehole has a 4” (10.16 cm) PVC tube sticking from the borehole where the original CORK was ripped out. This PVC pipe rises about 2 m above the ROV platform such that the ROV Jason had to hover to collect fluids. Near the base of the tube where it connects to the borehole is a mass of white material, presumable brucite or calcite. This mass appears to help seal the borehole as the borehole discharges nicely. When we arrived, there was a brucite chimney over the top of the PVC pipe, which is broken from an earlier expedition. When we pumped 1L/min the discharge stopped, suggesting that the actual discharge from the borehole is less than this rate. When we stopped pumping the discharge returned to its same intensity within minutes. We left this borehole as is (open). Given that the dissolved gas concentration of methane, pH, and alkalinity have not changed in 13 years at this site, this hole should remain discharging into the future. The only issue is that the PVC pipe is not robust. If it breaks off one will need a weighted intake that is at least 2 m long to get the intake into the casing to minimize mixing with seawater.

Outline of Jason Dives

For future reference, note that the best weather in the area is in the May/July timeframe.

Jason Dive 1468 – Big Blue - 11/21/22 10:00 PM local

U1496C 18°06.6068'N 147°06.1001'E 1243.17

We descended and located the wellhead. The ROV platform was beat up and not properly set. This happened when the drillship deployed the ROV platform. The platform was hung up in the moon pool and after a few waves it was on its way to the seafloor. At the seafloor the drill pipe was still in the borehole, but the platform was not positioned perfectly. At the start of this dive, we looked down the hole but could not tell if it was open. There were numerous active shrimp some rock lobsters and lots of fuzzy filaments on the ROV platform, consistent with fluid discharge and microbial growth. We went to the CORK-Lite and removed the 10 foot-long pole with tee handle and went back to the well head. We stuck the pole down the hole past where the CORK-Lite would be positioned. There was no resistance. However, there was mud in the reentry cone and on the landing seat. Mud was caked on and the 10-foot pole was not suited for the task of cleaning all of the mud. We went back to the CORK-lite, checked the weight of the CORK-Lite and floats and decided to release the weights. We estimated that the weight of the CORK-Lite and floats was 60-80 lb negative (the calculated weight was -78 lb). We lowered the CORK-Lite in the hole. We moved and bounced the CORK-Lite, but it did not want to seat. The latches are about 5 inches from the location where they would be set. There were no fluids coming out of the top of the CORK-Lite. We closed the valves and pumped water out of one of the ½ inch sample port. We stopped sampling to collect rocks and sediment cores. Then we returned to the wellhead and continued to pump. There were signs of white precipitate (smoke), but the samples were diluted fluids with the highest measured pH of ~9.5, well below the expected pH of 12.5.

During a survey we found the A and B holes. There was a small chimney in the B hole and Jeff took an ITG sample from a small orifice that was discharging white smoke. This sample was the best fluid sample from the area but still heavily diluted. Two rocks were collected. One push core was collected in the drill tailings. The remainder of the push cores were taken nearby. These cores had dark blue mud at the base of the cores.

Prior to releasing the floats, we did another survey to guide the future deployment of the German benthic station and our geodetic deployment. Around the wellhead there is a ~25-m perimeter with fresh serpentinite flow material with no “rocks” (some “rocks” are Mn-coated mud balls). To the north, the flow continues to about 50 m from the wellhead. There is a valley of mud between small mounds (1 m high) in a linear formation (herein referred as “valleys”) that extends to ~85 m to the NW. A similar valley extends to 45 m to the west. To the southwest the flow extends to 35 m. During this portion of the dive we collected another 5 rocks.

Near the end of the dive we opened the ball valve and there was constant white smoke discharging from the ball valve. The flow is slow, not like South Chamorro, but it exists!!!! We had the ball valve open for 20 plus minutes and most of the time we observed white smoke.

We released the floats and tried to move the CORK-Lite again. We looked at the base of the CORK-Lite within the re-entry cone and it is not latched, but at least we added another 600 lbs to push down on whatever was stopping the CORK-Lite from setting

Four IGTs were triggered, lots of HOG samples were collected including 3 copper samples, and 12 push cores and 10 rocks were collected.

We left the borehole with a filter in the ½ inch sample port and the other two ports and ball valve closed. The ½ inch valve to the seals remained open.

Jason Dive 1469 – Blue Moon 11/24/2022 2:00:00 PM local

U1492D 15°42.5694'N 147°10.5991'E 3666.44

We located the wellhead and looked in the re-entry cone with a camera on the manipulator. We could easily see the landing seal and there was no serpentinite in the cone, unlike Big Blue. Also unlike Big Blue there were no shrimp (maybe one or two), no lobsters, and the ROV platform looked clean. We recover the CORK Lite and brought it over with the ROV dive weights and 10-foot-long pole, because the projected weight was much less than the previous dive and I didn't want to take a chance with the CORK-Lite floating off - although it should have been the same weight as the previous deployment. Once we got the CORK-Lite to the wellhead we were able to get it past the ROV platform (which is not on center) and in the hole. It took about 2 hours to get the CORK-Lite situated correctly then with a flick of the wrist it fell into place and white brucite poured out of the ball valve. It was flowing at least an order of magnitude faster than at Big Blue and similar to what we observed at South Chamorro seamount where flow was 0.2 L/s. This flow rate is sufficient to flush the CORK-Lite in roughly 17 minutes. Instead of sampling right away we left for 30 minutes to observe other borehole locations (e.g., other boreholes). Upon returning there was a lot less smoke pouring out of the top of the ball valve. We collected water from the ½ inch sampling port. By the end of the dive we could count particles that were coming out of the borehole, yet the fluid results pointed toward seawater. The good news is that the CORK is sealed; however, we don't understand why seawater was initially flowing out the top of the CORK.

We collected 8 push cores near marker 13, which is in view from the wellhead (~20 m from the wellhead). Cores revealed a serpentinite flow over pelagic sediment. We didn't have time to go to J40-PC2, which had the fastest pore water seepage rate of the cores collected in 2003. No rocks were collected.

We left the borehole with each of the three-sample port closed and ball valve open. The ½ inch valve to the seals remained open.

Typical basket for the first three dives (J1468-J1470)

Jason Dive 1470 – Celestial 11/26/22 4:00 PM local

U1497D 16°32.2548'N 147°13.2621'E 2018.8

We descended on the wellhead and stuck the starboard manipulator below the ROV platform. The casing hanger was not set properly relative to the reentry cone. It should be lower than it is such that you cannot see the “teeth” on the hanger (see figure below). Ideally the hanger is lower allowing the pipe to slide into the borehole. We found the CORK-Lite, dropped one set of Jason dive weights and the 10-foot-long pole with a tee handle and moved the CORK-Lite into place. Akel got the CORK-Lite into the correct location on the second try. The camera on the starboard manipulator verified that it was seated. This hole did not look like it was producing water; however, at the end of the dive when the ITG samples were collected we observed flow from the top of the ball valve. Prior to collecting water samples, we observed the two nearby boreholes

and collected push core. Cores were collected at the bottom of a small valley. Sediments were sandy with less clay. Unfortunately, all fluid samples (HOG and ITG) were bottom seawater.

After collecting the HOG samples and prior to collecting the ITG samples we mapped the area around the wellhead to see where the best spot would be for the

geodetic survey and the German benthic station.

NE direction –valley where the push cores were taken, following another small valley that opened up to a flat mostly sedimented area, drop off at 50 m from the wellhead, rocks on the rim.

NW direction – up a hill to a valley, going up relatively smooth, cross a valley with rocks, at summit 50 m from wellhead, drops down and is more hummocky, steep slope down,

N direction – scattered boulders, down a ridge, small valley, fewer rocks, to the NW is smoother, drops off at 60 m from the wellhead, rock #4.

E direction – slopes down, large, scattered rocks, going downslope, valley, distance 25 meters, small ridge then up, some rocks, 30 m from wellhead, about 50 m from wellhead is a ridge.

SE direction – slopes, some big rocks, valley, lower to the left (E), black rocks, going up, sediment pond, more valleys, flat sediment, 30 m from the wellhead, ridge 35 m, drop off, in general good sediment away from the wellhead in this direction,

S Direction - slopes to right (W), ridge, small valley to south, rocky ridges, going uphill, small ridge, cliff, drops to a sharp edge of a cliff.

W direction – lots of small rocks, down to right (N), bowl of sediment to right, lots of sediment, 50 m away from the wellhead, topographical high, scattered rocks, valley.

Summary – best to be within 25 m of the wellhead. Shoot for the southeastern side. Also, the black rock are rocks or mud balls that are covered with Mn oxides. We picked up many black “rocks” but many broke when the manipulator was activated.

We left the borehole with each of the three-sample port closed and ball valve open. The ½ inch valve to the seals remained open.

Jason Dive 1471 – South Chamorro 11/28/22 12:00 PM local

1200C 13°47.0724'N 146°0.1717'E 2932.16

We descended to the wellhead and were relieved to see a brucite chimney at the top of the PVC pipe and to have the PVC pipe well above the ROV platform. It is so high up that the ROV cannot sit on the platform and collect water, so the ROV hovered. The outside of the PVC tubing also had long filamented microbes that excited some of the microbiologists. We tried to recover the brucite chimney but failed to get most of it. We did however succeed in getting some of it and stored it in a biobox. ITG and HOG samples were collected as well as push cores and 9 rocks.

The ITG samples recovered water with a pH of 12.15 and alkalinity of 120, identical to the fluids collected in 2009. The dissolved methane concentration was slightly higher at 23 $\mu\text{mol/kg}$. The bio samples from the HOG had a much higher pH than the chem samples from the HOG (12.0 versus 10.1, respectively, although the bio samples also had low pH values in the range of 9). The bio samples were collected first. To get better samples, the idea is to use a long intake and the fast pump to collect fluid. Essentially, we were pumping faster than the borehole could produce formation water.

The push cores had some light blue coloration near the bottom. Rocks varied from black-to-black interiors with and without visible planar minerals. All rocks were covered with a Mn coat.

Jason Dive 1472 – South Chamorro 11/28/22 12:00 PM local

1200C 13°47.0724'N 146°0.1717'E 2932.16

To get better fluids from the HOG we used a 9-foot-long intake. Note that the basket was similar to the picture to the right during the previous dive with the exception of replacing the scoop with a toilet brush and two intakes for the HOG to a single 9-foot-long intake. Upon reaching the wellhead we took a look at the base of the PVC pipe. There is a precipitate around the base of the PVC pipe, suggesting that at some point there was a leak in the pipe, probably after the modification during

Exp. 366. After 3 ITG samples were collected the 9-foot-long intake was placed down the PVC tubing. Operations included pumping for 5 minutes followed by waiting for 10 minutes. When the pumps were on venting stopped but venting quickly returned in a few minutes after the

pumps ceased. There was an issue with hydraulic fluid leaking to the ocean via the manipulators. The thought during the dive was that it was the port manipulator, thus no push cores could be collected. At the end of the HOG samples, we used a toilet brush to collect filaments along the PVC pipe and placed it in the biobox. No push cores or rock were collected, because of the manipulator issue.

All water samples had a pH of 12.1 to 12.4 and satisfied science needs. Thus, we were finished with South Chamorro Seamount. However, there was so much gas in these samples that most of the large bag sample containers were compromised, though the sample bags themselves remained intact.

Once on deck, it was determined that there was no water in the ROV's hydraulic system. The thought was that there was a seal that was broken in one of the manipulators. After dinner the ROV team operated both manipulators and replaced the one that was leaking oil. However, the new manipulator (direct from the factory) has issues – the wrist does not rotate without more power than is usually provided.

Waiting on Weather (WOW)

On Thursday December 1, 2022 we were in place for a dive on Blue Moon, but the swell was too large. As a result, we mapped the seafloor to keep the ship stable. The weather got worse, so we had to go behind Saipan to get out of the swell. We returned on Monday morning, but the seas were still too big. However, at 6 pm on Monday we attempted a launch, but the ship could not hold course when the port thruster was secured. Thus, the dive was aborted. By 6 AM Tuesday morning (December 6) we were ready to dive.

Jason Dive 1473 – Blue Moon 12/6/2022 7:00:00 AM local

U1492D 15°42.5694'N 147°10.5991'E 3666.44

The primary focus for this dive was to collect fluids and to measure pressure. We descended to the borehole and closed the valve. It was not obvious that fluids were discharging, but there were particles to suggest that fluids were discharging. We attached a flow indicator (only moves if the flow rate is 0.5 l/s). It did not move. We attached two pressure sensors. One for long term on the ¼ inch line and one for 16 minutes on the 1/8-inch line. The

values for both were open to gain access to the formation. After 16 minutes the short-term pressure gauge on the 1/8-inch line was removed and the valve was closed. The ball valve was opened, and the HOG insert was lowered into the borehole. As it was lowered a big plume of rust discharged from the borehole. This discharge lasted ~20 minutes providing some indication that the borehole was discharging (and potentially formation water). We spent the rest of the time using the HOG sampler to collect fluids by turning on the pump on for a few minutes, then letting the formation recover for 10 minutes. Near the end of the dive we removed the HOG's intake but we had to fly high and didn't see if there was a plume resulting from pulling the intake out of the borehole. We did a background check for the pressure sensor and closed the ball valve. The wellhead was left in a position that would be good if we don't get back to it.

Analysis on board the ship showed the best samples with a pH of 8.1 and much higher gas contents than were reported during the drilling expedition. Also, the pressure record indicates that the borehole may be barely over pressured (<1.2 kPa), consistent with the lack of extensive flow and a small percentage of formation fluid. This range was determined by the difference in pressure in the borehole and much later at the same depth as the Jannasch intake but in seawater. However, right after the ball valve was opened there is no statistical difference (closed vs open system) suggesting that we were measuring bottom seawater conditions. Either there is no flow or the ball valve leaks, which I doubt. Nevertheless, if the hole is overpressured, it is very small and would not support a lot of discharge.

Jason Dive 1474 – Big Blue - 12/7/22 12:00 PM local

U1496C 18°06.6068'N 147°06.1001'E 1243.17

This dive started with a look around the base of the wellhead and around the base of the CORK-Lite for fluid discharge. We did not observe discharge. Also, with the CORK sealed (with the exception of SPE extraction experiment) the shrimp that were present on the ROV platform were not moving like they did when we arrived prior to deploying the CORK-Lite. We then conducted some work at the wellhead, with the installation of two pressure recorders (one short term and the other long term). Prior to placing the sensor in the Jannasch connector, we waited 5 minutes

with the sensor just barely in the Jannasch connector. The short-term pressure sensor was placed in the 1/8 inch valve and the long term was placed in the 1/4 inch valve. The hold for the short-term pressure sensor was from 4:01:29 to 4:06:58 before the pressure sensor was pushed in and the valve was open at 4:07:44. The long-term pressure valve started the hold at the entrance of the Jannasch connector at 4:13:30 (ROV time); 2:13:30 PM local time. The long-term probe was inserted at 4:20:54 and the valve was opened to the sensor. This made room in the basket for us to remove

the extraction experiment and place it in one of the pressure holders. The 1/2 inch valve to the

extraction experiment was closed at 4:23:32 and the experiment removed at 4:24:46. The borehole was closed except for the two valves to the two pressure sensors and the valve that goes to the latches. The ball valve was then opened at 4:46:00 to vent freely. Particles were discharging, but the plume was lacking in comparison to the one at South Chamorro. Two IGTs were collected in the ball valve.

We then went to the B-Hole and placed a 8” PVC cap over the site that was discharging fluid on the previous dive to this site. After a while an ITG was collected. We then used the PVC cap as a shovel and dug a deeper hole. The surface has a cemented layer that was several centimeters thick crust. We collected some. After excavation we place the 5-gallon bucket in the hole and went back to the wellhead to deploy markers.

Markers were deployed by first hovering over the ball valve on the CORK-Lite and centering the ball valve such that it was in the middle of the retracted basket and just under the front portion of the basket. We then proceeded 15, 25, 50, and 75 m from the wellhead in N, S, E, and W directions, and place a marker into the seafloor. All ROV movements used computer commands (no joystick). An image of the marker was taken to verify how deep it was buried in the sediment. At the end of a transect, we turned 180 degrees and backtracked our course to verify that the markers were in a line. From the N line, we started at 15 m (marker at 20.5 cm), then traveled up a hill to the 25 m location (marker at 14.8 cm).

At 50 m the nice new serpentinite flow, which was consistent to this point, was diminished, and rougher, more “aged”

crust became prevalent (marker at 54.5 cm). At 75 m the marker was in 88 cm. From the South line, 15 m from the wellhead the marker was at 84.5 cm in very fluffy sediment. This site had new sediment that continued to 25 m with the marker in at 87 cm. At 50 m the sediment was very fluffy, and the marker went in to 55.5 cm. The features on the seafloor could be little slumps in this fluffy sediment. The surface doesn't look like "ripples" from ocean currents. At 75 m there were lots of Mn-covered rocks and mud balls and the marker was in at 84 cm. To the east the 15 m location was half smooth and half rubble with fluffy sediment overlaying a harder substrate (marker to 52.2 cm). At 25 m the sediment was fluffy but more brown/green in color (marker to 83 cm). At 50 m we observed scattered rocks without the recent serpentinite flow and some black (Mn-covered) rocks (marker at 20 cm). We then went uphill to marker 75, there was new (smooth) sediment, and the marker went in to 19 cm. To the West, there was smooth sediment and the marker at 15 m went in fluffy sediment to 86 cm. At 25 m the sediment was super fluffy and there was a small valley, and the marker went in to 23 cm. At 50 m the sediment was fluffy but there were rocks, and the marker was set to 87 cm. We did not have another marker for the 75 m distance. However, past the 50 m location was a slight wall with more relief.

We returned to the wellhead to remove the short-term pressure sensor at 9:05:36 ROV time (7:05:32 PM local time) and headed past the B-Hole by about 15 m to the north to collect 4 push cores. Then we went to the B-Hole for a HOG pumped sample. We returned to the wellhead and tried two pumping regiments to see which works better. The DO sensor moved from 133 μM (bottom water) to about 100 μM in the best case. The dive ended by tripping the Niskin bottles (both) and observing the 5-gallon bucket, which did not spark joy.

Jason Dive 1475 – Big Blue - 12/8/22 8:00 PM local

U1496C 18°06.6068'N 147°06.1001'E 1243.17

The focus was to collect a good fluid. Upon arriving at the site ITG samples were collected. These ITG samplers had an additional 10-in-long tubing attached to the snorkel to collect fluids with the thought of getting past any mixing associated with the ball valve. Then the HOG sampler was used. The HOG had an intake that was 30 feet long from the top of the CORK-Lite. This is at least 12 feet below the bottom of the CORK-Lite. DO measurements were low with initial collections having a DO value of 30 μM compared to bottom seawater at 133 μM . With time the DO decreased to 7 and there were "puffs" of white smoke (brucite) at the exhaust port of the HOG. The lowest DO value was 0.9 μM . This suggest that the base of the CORK-Lite provides a pathway for bottom seawater to enter the CORK-Lite body. We know the CORK-Lite is not sealed given its position and based on the initial visual inspection. Also because of this discontinuity in casing/CORK-Lite, the pressure sensor will only measure bottom seawater conditions and not the actual overpressure within the borehole. Thus, pressure data will act as an indicator of how the borehole moves in response to earthquakes and other physical forcing. We spent lots of time collecting water. The HOG recovered fluids with a pH of 12.4-12.5 but the IGTs didn't. After this dive we modified the exhaust of the HOG sample pump to vent into a reservoir that could be sampled by the IGTs. After water sampling, we collected a series of push cores about 10 m SE of the Hole 1496B and recovered the Home Depot bucket from Hole 1496B. Then we transited to the dart, which was where it was anticipated to be. The dart hit a rock and fell over. The spear was intact, it just doesn't look that way in the pictures. Afterwards

we went back to Hole 1496B and headed north. We quickly got away from the fresh flow into older flows, some with organisms. The end of the line was about 100 m north of the wellhead.

Jason Dive 1476 – Celestial 12/10/22 8:00 PM local

U1497D 16°32.2548'N 147°13.2621'E 2018.8

We descended upon the CORK-Lite at Celestial, which was left open since J1470 (two weeks ago). Much to our surprise we approached and saw water discharging from the ball valve. The ball valve had a fine layer of orangish dusting (Fe oxide) on the shiny stainless-steel valve and small particles that discharged. With this surprise we changed our operational schedule to go from a 12-hour dive to a 30-hour dive. Two IGT samples were collected in the ball valve, then the 30-foot-long HOG intake was placed in the hole. This time the exhaust of the HOG sample pump ended in a reservoir on the front basket where the IGTs could be sampled. When formation waters are pumped into this reservoir, they were cloudy with an orangish tint – like the top of the ball valve, indicating that there is some iron associated with the wellhead fluids and likely brucite formation. With a combination of pumping and letting the reservoir recharge, the DO remained in the range of 30 to 40 (relative to 133). A lot of HOG samples were collected and two more IGTs

were collected in the reservoir at the end of the HOG line. At the end of the dive we inserted two pressure sensors, one for the short term (inserted at 20:47:40 with the valve opened at 20:48:18) and one to be left on the seafloor for years (inserted at 20:37:50 with the valve opened at 20:38:15). The ball valve was closed at 20:50:46 (7:50:46 local) and we left the short-term pressure sensor in for 10 minutes before recovering it (Valve closed at 21:00:30 and the handle removed at 20:01:10). Note that the CORK-Lite at Celestial has two ¼ inch sample ports whereas the other two have one ¼ inch port and one 1/8 inch port. The dive ended with the ball valve closed and the only sample port that was left open was the one with the long-term pressure sensor. The ½ inch valve to the seals remained open.

Samples were analyzed on board and revealed a maximum pH of 8, much lower than anticipated. Also, the dissolved methane was low but measurable. It appears that we collected seawater that has reacted with steel casing. The question is, why are we observing discharge from the ball valve?

The pressure record showed no difference between the fully sealed borehole and the open borehole with the ball valve opened. The lack of an overpressure suggests that there was no flow.

Signs of fluid discharge were likely the Bernoulli effect of a cross flow affecting the volume within a pipe. Alternatively, the borehole is not sealed; however, this borehole is sealed beneath the seafloor as designed and there is no reason to suspect failure in the ball valves or the sampling ports.

Jason Dive 1477 – Big Blue - 12/13/22 12:00 AM local

U1496C 18°06.6068'N 147°06.1001'E 1243.17

The goal of this dive was to get good IGT samples and to collect more water and particles. The dive started with the deployment of a long-term pressure sensor. Then we lowered the 30-foot-long HOG intake into the well. We sampled formation fluids for hours. The copper tubes were filled followed by four IGT samples and the rest of the HOG samples. It took 5 hours to fill one filter, with a combination of pumping and letting the formation recover. We did a test by putting a sterivex filter in line with a bag to make sure the formation water was passing through the filter. There was a lot of white precipitate, just like the previous dive at this location. After water sampling we drove about 50 m north and collected 7 push cores. We ventured further into the old material and collected a “rock”. This terrain had slabs of “rock” that were angled, much like the crust around the B Hole when we excavated. We collected a piece of the slab “rock”, which was difficult to remove. We think the slab (and all of the other slabs) of “rock” is lithified mud that has subsequently been disturbed during an uplifting/eruption event. At the end of the dive, we were west of the CORK-Lite on a steep hill where there is evidence of “rock” slides. We drove eastward towards the CORK-Lite and ended the dive at Markers 6 and 10, about 1 m apart.

Jason Dive 1478 – Blue Moon 11/14/2022 4:00:00 AM local

U1492D 15°42.5694'N 147°10.5991'E 3666.44

We descended to the wellhead and opened the ball valve. A big cloud of rusty water discharged from the open borehole and continued for about 20 minutes after which there was no apparent discharge. HOG sampling occurred but oxygen values did not drop. After hours of pumping and waiting, the copper samples and IGTs were collected using the HOG. More HOG sampling continued until near the end of the dive. When the HOG intake was removed there was a cloud of particles that discharged during and after the removal of the intake. Valves were closed (except for the pressure sensor and the latch) and we went to take push cores at the J40 PC2 location; however, this didn't look like a “fresh” flow and there were many rocks in the area. We then headed to the B hole and located it. We searched for the dart, but could not find it, so we conducted a search grid that included the B hole to the SE. The dart was located. It is vertical and sticking in the mud but the mud skirt was exposed. We used the same transponder on each deployment and drove directly to the first dart. However, the actual location was ~35 m different than the location that was provided by the transponder at release (estimated to be 121 m at a heading of 345 degrees from the wellhead). The location of the dart on the seafloor was 15.7108417 degrees N 147.176243 degrees east. We then move back towards the B hole and collected six push cores in an area that had a smooth surface of mud but small particles on the surface. Mud in the push cores appears to be brown in color.

Outline of CORK-Lite deployments

Deployment of CORK-Lites 2022

Figure - Diagram of CORK-Lite and floats during deployment. Weights were based on original estimates.

Three CORK-Lites were prepared in accordance to directions provided by Tom Pettigrew. We also added a 10-foot-long pipe with tee handle to ream out a potential chimney in the casing. It was held against the side of the CORK-Lite with two bungee cords and pull pins. We used three other pull pins. One pull pin held the boot in place and was secured with about 4-5 sets of rubber bands. The other two pull pins were used to attach the 1-m-long polypro ropes to the CORK-Lite. These pull pins were

also held in place with 5-6 rubber band for each tee handle as we didn't want them to come out when we picked up the CORK-Lite off the deck.

The first part of the operations was to deploy the floats from the stern. The ship was positioned one nautical mile downstream and approached the drop zone at a speed of 0.5 knots. The drop zone was 50 m north of the wellhead at each site. The upper float was released first with the rest of the floats deployed one after the other (they were connected prior to deployment on the deck). Once all of the floats were in the water, we picked up the CORK-Lite and got it over the side of the ship. Then we added dive weights (three sets of two Jason weights, 16 pounds each for a total of 96 pounds) and held the weights in place with a bungee cord and pull pin. Then the line to the floats were attached to a D-ring just above the lifting bar. When we were on station the package was released. Decent rates were on the order of 90-100 meters per minute. After the first two deployments we added a third 5-m-long spectra line between the large float and the bail on the top of the CORK-Lite.

Once on the bottom we located the CORK-Lites using the beacon from the Jason group. The package was 200 m SE of the wellhead at Big Blue, 80 m SW of the wellhead at Blue Moon, and 80 m to the northwest at Celestial. Once the packages were located, we lifted each off the

seafloor to estimate the entire weight. At Big Blue the CORK-Lite minus the boot and dive weights were 60-80 pounds negative about 9 pounds lighter than expected. At Blue Moon the weights were questionable so we left the dive weights on the CORK-Lite as we transported it to the wellhead. At Celestial the projected weight was 200 pounds negative prior to the release of the weights, boot, and pole. Thus, we released the boot, deposited the pole on the seafloor and removed one set of dive weights. This would suggest that we were 37 pounds lighter than anticipated. Note that the big float was estimated to be 400 pounds buoyant, and I downgraded it to 385 pounds at North Pond (5000 m). Thus, the entire package of floats that were used are likely to be 691 pounds with the large float being 400 pounds.

Thus, for future use note that the one needs about account for depth and to have flexibility of weights and buoyance of at least 50 pounds if not 96 pounds as we had in this case.

Outline of Benthic Pressure Stations Operations

82A

The first benthic station (lawn dart) was deployed on Thursday December 8, 2022. The target was 30 m to the north of the wellhead (U1496C) on Big Blue. We had an issue with the acoustic release, it released the spectra rope that was holding the dart to the acoustic release. Luckily the lip of the dart caught the edge of the ship and tag lines prevented it from prematurely ascending. The Dart was lowered using a d-ring in the bite. The dart was lowered to 1100 m at which time the acoustic release was activated. However, the release didn't work on the first time, nor the fifth. It took some time and several deck boxes, then the weight on the wire changed, indicating that the dart was free. Based on the last few transponder locations, the Dart was released about 55 m from the wellhead (to the NE at 070 degrees; 18.11027N 147.10259E). On J1475 we located the dart (essentially the location from the transponder). It appears the dart hit a rock and fell over. We used the temperature probe to verify that the spear was attached.

82B

The second benthic station was deployed on Celestial Seamount. The dart was lowered to 1800 m water depth and the acoustic release worked the first time, releasing the float. The ship held station throughout the deployment. The location at the time of release was 16.536758 degrees N 147.2214510 degrees east. This location is 103 m southeast (heading 155 degrees) of the CORK-Lite.

Genius Plug

The third benthic station was deployed on Blue Moon Seamount. The dart was lowered to 3500 m water depth and the acoustic release worked the first time, releasing the dart. The ship held station throughout the deployment. The location of the dart on the seafloor was 15.7108417 degrees N 147.176243 degrees east. This location is 156 m north northwest (heading 344 degrees) of the CORK-Lite at Hole U1492D and 72 m northwest (heading 319) of Hole U1492B. The dart is standing upright, but the mud skirt is in the water column not on the sediment.

CTD Operations

KN-CTD-VO1

The only CTD was collected to the SE of Big Blue at 17 58.901'N 147 12.298'E in a water depth of ~3750 m. Niskin bottles were triggered at three depths (3667, 2400, and 1250 m), corresponding to the depths of the three serpentinite seamounts in which we installed a CORK-Lite. The CTD started at 4:56 local time on December 8, 2022.

Timeline of Operations

Cruise Log

KM2214 Mariana CORK-Lite

Event	Duration		Local Time	Local Time
	(hrs)	(days)	StartDayTime	EndDayTime
Transit - 312 nM	32	1.33	11/20/22 8:00 AM	11/21/22 4:00 PM
CORK Lite Deployment	3	0.13	11/21/22 4:00 PM	11/21/22 7:00 PM
Ship Positioning	1	0.04	11/21/22 7:00 PM	11/21/22 8:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1468	2	0.08	11/21/22 8:00 PM	11/21/22 10:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1468 Big Blue	34.5	1.44	11/21/22 10:00 PM	11/23/22 8:30 AM
Recover floats	3	0.13	11/23/22 8:30 AM	11/23/22 11:30 AM
Transit to Blue Moon 143 nM	13	0.54	11/23/22 11:30 AM	11/24/22 12:30 AM
Multi Beam mapping	7.5	0.31	11/24/22 12:30 AM	11/24/22 8:00 AM
CORK Lite Deployment	4	0.17	11/24/22 8:00 AM	11/24/22 12:00 PM
Jason Prep	2	0.08	11/24/22 12:00 PM	11/24/22 2:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1469 Blue Moon	18.5	0.77	11/24/22 2:00 PM	11/25/22 8:30 AM
recover floats	2.5	0.10	11/25/22 8:30 AM	11/25/22 11:00 AM
Transit to Celestial and multi beam	21	0.88	11/25/22 11:00 AM	11/26/22 8:00 AM
CORK Lite Deployment	8	0.33	11/26/22 8:00 AM	11/26/22 4:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1470 Celestial	20.5	0.85	11/26/22 4:00 PM	11/27/22 12:30 PM
recover floats	2	0.08	11/27/22 12:30 PM	11/27/22 2:30 PM
Transit to S Chamorro and multi beam	21.5	0.90	11/27/22 2:30 PM	11/28/22 12:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1471 South Chamorro	16	0.67	11/28/22 12:00 PM	11/29/22 4:00 AM
mapping east to the trench	12	0.50	11/29/22 4:00 AM	11/29/22 4:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1472 South Chamorro	24	1.00	11/29/22 4:00 PM	11/30/22 4:00 PM
analytical period wait for decision	2	0.08	11/30/22 4:00 PM	11/30/22 6:00 PM
Transit to Blue Moon	26	1.08	11/30/22 6:00 PM	12/1/22 8:00 PM
Multi Beam mapping (WOW)	10	0.42	12/1/22 8:00 PM	12/2/22 6:00 AM
head to Siapan (WOW)	58	2.42	12/2/22 6:00 AM	12/4/22 4:00 PM
Transit to Blue Moon (WOW)	14	0.58	12/4/22 4:00 PM	12/5/22 6:00 AM
Wait on Weather Blue Moon (WOW)	12.5	0.52	12/5/22 6:00 AM	12/5/22 6:30 PM
mapping (WOW)	12.5	0.52	12/5/22 6:30 PM	12/6/22 7:00 AM
Jason Dive, 1473 Blue Moon	13	0.54	12/6/22 7:00 AM	12/6/22 8:00 PM
Transit to Big Blue	16	0.67	12/6/22 8:00 PM	12/7/22 12:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1474 Big Blue	20	0.83	12/7/22 12:00 PM	12/8/22 8:00 AM
Lawn Dart	5	0.21	12/8/22 8:00 AM	12/8/22 1:00 PM
CTD Hydrocast	7	0.29	12/8/22 1:00 PM	12/8/22 8:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1475 Big Blue	36	1.50	12/8/22 8:00 PM	12/10/22 8:00 AM
Transit to Celestial and multi beam	12	0.50	12/10/22 8:00 AM	12/10/22 8:00 PM
Jason Dive, 1476 Celestial	36	1.50	12/10/22 8:00 PM	12/12/22 8:00 AM

Dart on Celestial	4	0.17	12/12/22 8:00 AM	12/12/22 12:00 PM
transit 94 nm	12	0.50	12/12/22 12:00 PM	12/13/22 12:00 AM
Jason Dive, 1477 Big Blue	32	1.33	12/13/22 12:00 AM	12/14/22 8:00 AM
Transit to Blue Moon 143 nm (16 Hrs)	16	0.67	12/14/22 8:00 AM	12/15/22 12:00 AM
Dart on Blue Moon	4	0.17	12/15/22 12:00 AM	12/15/22 4:00 AM
Jason Dive, 1478 Blue Moon	21	0.88	12/15/22 4:00 AM	12/16/22 1:00 AM
Transit to Guam - 197 nautical miles	29	1.21	12/16/22 1:00 AM	12/17/22 6:00 AM

Multibeam Mapping Operations

We covered kilometers of seafloor with the multibeam system on. Most of the data were collected at 11 knots. Because it took 12 hours to turn around the HOG and ITG samplers, we had the flexibility to transit among the four wellheads. Big Blue to Celestial took 12 hours to transit. Big Blue to Blue Moon took 16 hours to transit. Blue Moon to South Chamorro took about 12 hours to transit. However, some of the dedicated track lines were collected at 8 knots while we were waiting on weather (WOW) or to fill in a 12-hour period. Many of these dedicated multibeam lines started and ended at Blue Moon. This image was captured during a transit to Blue Moon and does not include the transit into Guam at the end of the expedition. Initial estimate is 7.25 days of usable multibeam data.

Marianas Serpentinizing Seamounts
HOG fluid sample log

Sample ID	Site	Date (UTC)	Lat	Long	Heading	Depth (m)	Start Time (UTC)	End Time (UTC)	Sample type	Collected Volume (L)	Comment
J1468_C1	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	18:23	18:31	2L fluid for chem	1900	No sample
J1468_C2	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	18:32	18:40	2L fluid for chem	1900	
J1468_C3	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	15:05	15:13	2L fluid for chem	1900	
J1468_C4	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	15:54	16:02	2L fluid for chem	1900	
J1468_C5	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	16:43	16:51	2L fluid for chem	1900	
J1468_C6	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	16:52	17:01	2L fluid for chem	1900	
J1468_LV 7	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	19:23	20:01	9 L for chem	9000	bulkhead fitting leaky
J1468_LV 13	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	16:04	16:42	9 L for chem	9000	
J1468_LV 16	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	18:43	19:21	9L for bio	9000	
J1468_LV 17	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	17:02	?	9L for bio	?	
J1468_Cu 22	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	15:26	--	Copper	--	flushed w/ 2L water; stopped pump before closing
J1468_Cu 23	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	15:40	--	Copper	--	flushed w/ 2L water; stopped pump before closing
J1468_Cu 24	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	15:51	--	Copper	--	flushed w/ 2L water; stopped pump before closing
J1468_B8	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	22:58	23:07	2L fluid for bio	1900	
J1468_B9	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	6:22	6:30	2L fluid for bio	1900	
J1468_RF 10	U1496C (Big Blue)	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	RNA later flat filters		
J1468_RF 11	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	21:17	21:28	RNA later flat filters	1340	stopped b/c minimum flow rate reached
J1468_RF 12	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	23:10	23:24	RNA later flat filters	1909	stopped b/c minimum flow rate reached
J1468_RF 14	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	2:19	2:45	RNA later flat filters	3507	stopped b/c minimum flow rate reached
J1468_LV 15	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	5:43	6:21	9L on bio intake!!	9000	
J1468_SF18	U1496C (Big Blue)	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	Sterivex	--	
J1468_SF19	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	21:30	22:54	Sterivex	20,001	
J1468_SF 20	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-21	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	23:26	2:14	Sterivex	40,002	
J1468_SF 21	U1496C (Big Blue)	2022-11-22	18.11004	147.1017	353	1236.8	2:51	5:40	Sterivex	40,002	
J1469_C1	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	12:24	12:32	2L bag	1900	main stem pump @1L/min while sampling
J1469_C2	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	12:33	12:41	2L bag	1900	main stem pump off while sampling
J1469_C3	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	17:26	17:34	2L bag	1900	1st sample after replacing the chem port. Flushed main stem @1L/min for 10 min before sampling & during sampling
J1469_C4	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	17:44	17:52	2L bag	1900	stopped flow through main stem 10 minutes before starting sample. Kept off while collecting @250 mL/min
J1469_C5	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	18:34	18:42	2L bag	1900	no main stem flush on since 17:34
J1469_C6	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	20:56		2L bag		flushed main stem @ 1.5 L/min for 15 min before & during collecting sample
J1469_LV 7	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	18:43	19:22	9L bag, C	9000	no main stem flush on since 17:34
J1469_LV 16	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	19:23	20:01	9L bag, B	9000	no main stem flush on since 17:34
J1469_LV 17	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	20:02	20:40	9L bag, B	9000	no main stem flush on since 17:34
J1469_Cu 22	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	18:00	--	Cu	--	flushed line @250 mL/min for 2L w/o main stem pump on
J1469_Cu 23	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	18:17	--	Cu	--	flushed line @250 mL/min for 2L w/o main stem pump on
J1469_Cu 24	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	18:29	--	Cu	--	flushed line @250 mL/min for 2L w/o main stem pump on
J1469_B8	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	12:56	13:04	2Lbag, B	1900	Main stem pump off; sampled by only pulling with sample pump
J1469_B9	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	16:54	17:02	2Lbag, B	1900	main stem @1L/min
J1469_RF 10	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	blank control		RNA filter	--	accidentally pumped 35 mL, but valve closed
J1469_RF 11	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	13:04	13:55	RNA filter	10000	Main stem pump off; sample pump flow rate @ end of sample 179 mL/min (down from 250 mL/min)
J1469_RF 12	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	14:44	15:24	RNA filter	8360	main stem @ 1L/min; flow down to 189 mL/min by end, so stopped early to get more water through other filters
J1469_RF 14	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	16:10	16:53	RNA filter	8844	main stem @1L/min; flow down to 191 mL/min by end; stopped for time
J1469_SF18	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660			Blank control Sterivex	??	Pumped! While flushing main stem @ 1L/min
J1469_SF19	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	ow obstruction		sterivex	--	first try: main stem not pumping; error of sudden flow obstruction when tried sampling. Second try: sudden flow obstruction
J1469_SF 20	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	14:00	14:42	sterivex	10000	first try: main stem not pumping; error of sudden flow obstruction when tried sampling. Second try turned main stem pumping on at 1L/min and sample restarted 250 mL/min & working okay now.
J1469_SF 21	U1492 (Blue Moon)	2022-11-24	15.70953	147.1767	172.8	3660	15:27	16:08	sterivex	10000	main stem @ 1L / min
J1470_C1	Celestial / U1496C	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	17:18	17:26	2L fluid for chem	1900	249.2 final flow rate
J1470_C3	Celestial / U1496C	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	18:03	18:11	2L fluid for chem	1900	249.2 final flow rate
J1470_C5	Celestial / U1496C	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	19:32	19:41	2L fluid for chem	1900	249.2 final flow rate
J1470_LV 7	Deep Seawater	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	20:51	21:30	9 L for chem	9000	See sample sheet - deep seawater!!
J1470_LV 16	Celestial / U1496C	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	18:13	18:52	9L for bio	9000	249.2 final flow rate
J1470_LV 17	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	18:53	19:30	9L for bio	9000	249.2 final flow rate
J1470_Cu 22	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	17:29	17:37	Copper	2000	249.2 final flow rate
J1470_Cu 23	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	17:39	17:47	Copper	2000	249.2 final flow rate
J1470_Cu 24	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	17:50	17:58	Copper	2000	249.2 final flow rate
J1470_B8	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	11:25	11:33	2L fluid for bio	1900	
J1470_B9	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	16:44	16:53	2L fluid for bio	1900	
J1470_RF 10	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012			RNA later flat filters		
J1470_RF 11	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	11:36	12:16	RNA later flat filters	10000	
J1470_RF 12	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	12:51	13:37	RNA later flat filters	10000	
J1470_RF 14	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	12:51	13:37	RNA later flat filters	10000	
J1470_SF18	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012			Sterivex		
J1470_SF19	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	12:20	12:48	Sterivex	6078	stopped early b/c pump rate going down; never above 245 mL/min

J1470_SF 20	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	13:39	14:29	Sterivex	10019	started 250 mL/min; ended 181.6 mL/min
J1470_SF 21	Celestial / U1497D	2022-11-26	16.5378	147.2213	174	2012	15:19	16:43	Sterivex	15000	final flow rate 151.4 mL/min
J1471_C2	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	5:54		2L fluid for chem	1900	
J1471_C4	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	8:45	8:53	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1471_C6	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	10:46	10:53	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1471_LV 7	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	8:55	9:31	9L for chem	8500	
J1471_LV 16	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	9:32	10:08	9L for bio	8500	
J1471_LV 17	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	10:08	10:45	9L for bio	8500	
J1471_Cu 22	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	11:12		copper		
J1471_Cu 23	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	11:21		copper		
J1471_Cu 24	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	11:37		copper		
J1471_B8	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	6:18	6:26	2L for bio	2570	
J1471_B9	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	8:19	8:27	2L for bio	1800	
J1471_RF 10	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926			RNA later control	0	
J1471_RF 11	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	6:30	6:31	RNA later flat filters	248	
J1471_RF 12	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	7:42	:(RNA later flat filters	38	
J1471_SF18	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926			control sterivex	0	
J1471_SF19	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	6:36	7:36	sterivex	13380	
J1471_SF 20	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	8:09	:(sterivex	1536	
J1471_SF 21	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-28	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	8:29	:(sterivex		
J1472_C2	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	9:17	9:35	2L fluid for chem	1600	sample lost; bag burst due to gas
J1472_C4	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	20:40	20:55	2L fluid for chem	1600	sample lost; bag burst due to gas
J1472_C6	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	23:58	0:19	2L fluid for chem	1600	
J1472_LV 7	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	9:46	11:35	9 L for chem	8000	
J1472_LV 16	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	11:50	13:40	9L for bio	8000	
J1472_LV 17	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	13:50	15:41	9L for bio	8000	
J1472_Cu 22	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	15:55	16:15	Copper		
J1472_Cu 23	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	16:26	16:46	Copper		
J1472_Cu 24	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	17:06	17:27	Copper		
J1472_B8	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-30	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	1:58	2:20	2L fluid for bio	1762	
J1472_B9	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-30	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	3:46	3:52	2L fluid for bio	1600	
J1472_SF18	S. Chamorro / U1200C		13.78459	146.0029	4	2926			Control Sterivex	0	
J1472_SF19	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-29	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	17:34	23:16	Sterivex	20000	
J1472_SF 20	S. Chamorro / U1200C	2022-11-30	13.78459	146.0029	4	2926	0:30	3:45	Sterivex	10000	
J1473_C1	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	1:20	1:31	2L fluid for chem	1639	1st flushed 2L thorough main stem @1L / min.
J1473_C2	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	1:37	1:53	2L fluid for chem	1626	
J1473_C3	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	7:03	7:21	2L fluid for chem	1800	900 mL + 900 mL
J1473_B4	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	3:57	4:15	2L fluid for bio	1800	900 mL + 900 mL
J1473_B5	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	4:25	4:44	2L fluid for bio	1700	900 + 833 mL
J1473_LV 7	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	2:06	2:55	9 L for chem	4064	1019 + 1007 + 1011 + 1027
J1473_B8	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	6:36	6:54	2L fluid for bio	1800	900 mL + 900 mL
J1473_B9	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	not sampled		2L fluid for bio		
Port 14									flow through for O2 reading & flushing		
J1473_SF18	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	control		Sterivex		
J1473_SF19	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	4:54	5:38	Sterivex	4000	1L + 1L + 1L
J1473_SF 20	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	5:50	6:25	Sterivex	3000	1L + 1L + 1L
J1473_SF 21	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	not sampled		Sterivex		
J1473_Cu 22	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	not sampled		Copper		
J1473_Cu 23	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	3:03		Copper	2036	1011 flushed; Cu closed. Cu opened, another 1025 flushed. Cu closed
J1473_Cu 24	Blue Moon / U1492D	2022-12-06	15.70957	147.1766	152	3659	3:30		Copper	2064	1019 flushed; Cu closed. Cu opened, another 1055 flushed. Cu closed
J1474_C1	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	10:17	10:32	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1474_C2	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	10:42	10:58	2L fluid for chem	1500	
J1474_C3	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	19:12	19:30	2L fluid for chem	1500	
J1474_C4	B-hole (bucket)	2022-12-07	18.110286	47.102268	13.2	1236.9	9:44	9:57	2L fluid for chem	1407	
J1474_C5	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	19:43	19:51	2L fluid for bio	1500	
J1474_B6	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	12:26	12:33	2L fluid for bio	1500	
J1474_LV 7	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	11:09	12:10	9 L for chem	5000	
J1474_B8	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	15:34	15:41	2L fluid for bio	1500	
J1474_SF18	1496C / Big Blue				21.8	1234			Sterivex		
J1474_SF19	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	12:33	18:56	Sterivex	35000	
J1474_SF 20	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	14:03	18:33	Sterivex	40000	
J1474_Cu 22	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	16:58	17:08	Copper	2000	
J1474_Cu 23	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	17:09	17:18	Copper	2000	
J1474_Cu 24	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-07	18.110301	47.101741	21.8	1234	17:19	17:29	Copper	2000	
J1475_C1	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	12:41	12:58	2L fluid for chem	1576	
J1475_C2	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	13:08	13:24	2L fluid for chem	1456	
J1475_C3	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	13:36	13:54	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1475_C4	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-09	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	8:14	8:30	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1475_C5	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-09	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	18:32	18:49	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1475_LV7	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	14:15	16:28	9L for bio	6000	20 min wait between 1L pumps
J1475_B8	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	21:27	21:44	2L for bio	1500	
J1475_B9	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-09	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	17:00	17:19	2L for bio	1500	
J1475_LV15	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	16:49	18:50	9L for bio	6000	20 min wait between 1L pumps
J1475_LV16	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	8:40	10:00	9L for bio	6100	
J1475_LV17	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	10:12	11:35	9L for bio	6000	

J1475_SF18	1496C / Big Blue	control	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	control		Sterivex		
J1475_SF19	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	21:58	2:55	Sterivex	24000	20 L at start of dive; 4L at end of dive
J1475_SF20	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-09	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	3:06	8:01	Sterivex	20000	
J1475_SF 21	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-09	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	11:46	16:49	Sterivex	20000	
J1475_Cu 22	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	19:11	19:40	Copper	2000	
J1475_Cu 23	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	20:00	20:29	Copper	2000	
J1475_Cu 24	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-08	18.110301	47.101741	318	1235	20:48	21:16	Copper	2000	
J1476_C1	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	13:22	13:40	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1476_C2	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	13:51	14:08	2L fluid for chem	1500	
J1476_C3	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	15:54	16:18	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1476_C4	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	21:56	22:14	2L fluid for chem	1600	
J1476_C5	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	4:37	4:56	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1476_C6	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	7:38	7:57	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1476_B8	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	19:36	19:57	2L for bio	1800	
J1476_B9	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	18:06	18:13	2L for bio	1600	
J1476_C10	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	10:36	10:54	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1476_C11	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	15:04	15:23	2L fluid for chem	1600	
J1476_C12	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	18:24	18:43	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1476_C13	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	18:54	19:16	2L fluid for chem	1800	
Port 14	Celestial / U1497D		16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012			straight connection flow through		
J1476_LV15	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	11:04	12:50	9L for bio	8000	
J1476_LV16	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	13:00	14:53	9L for bio	8000	
J1476_SF18	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	16:29	21:44	Sterivex	20000	
J1476_SF19	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	22:33	3:24	Sterivex	20000	
J1476_SF20	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	5:07	7:28	Sterivex	20000	
J1476_SF 21	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-11	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	15:34	7:28	Sterivex	13000	
J1476_Cu 22	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	14:08	14:44	Copper	3000	
J1476_Cu 23	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	14:55	15:17	Copper	2000	
J1476_Cu 24	Celestial / U1497D	2022-12-10	16.537625	47.221066	215.4	2012	15:29	15:48	Copper	2000	
J1476_C1	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	15:44	16:00	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1476_C2	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	10:00	10:16	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1476_C3	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	16:11	16:31	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1476_C4	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-13	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	0:25	0:41	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1476_C5	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-13	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	4:33	4:51	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1476_C6	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	10:28	10:47	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1476_C7	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	19:03	19:20	2L fluid for chem	1400	
J1476_LV13	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-13	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	6:18	7:22	9L for bio	5000	
Port 14									straight connection flow through		
J1476_LV15	1496C / Big Blue						no pump - control		9L for bio - control		
J1476_LV16	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-13	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	8:39	9:40	9L for bio	5000	
J1476_LV17	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-13	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	7:34	8:28	9L for bio	5000	
J1476_SF18	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	19:24	0:16	Sterivex	20000	
J1476_SF19	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-13	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	0:50	5:02	Sterivex	20000	
J1476_SF20	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-13	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	10:57	16:04	Sterivex	20000	
J1476_SF 21	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235	16:19	18:52	Sterivex	12000	
J1476_Cu 22	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235		17:04	Copper		
J1476_Cu 23	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235		17:33	Copper		
J1476_Cu 24	1496C / Big Blue	2022-12-12	18.11008	147.1012	317	1235		18:03	Copper		
J1478_C1	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-14	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	21:15	21:28	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C2	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-14	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	21:50	22:13	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C3	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-14	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	22:24	22:41	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C4	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	2:34	2:53	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C5	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	3:03	3:22	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C6	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	3:32	3:52	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C7	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	4:01	4:16	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C8	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	5:49	6:12	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C9	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	7:36	7:54	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C10	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	8:09	8:24	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C11	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	8:34	8:53	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C12	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	5:08	5:39	sterivex + fluid for che	1800	sterivex inline before bag
J1478_C13	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	9:03	9:20	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C14	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	9:30	9:49	2L fluid for chem	1800	
J1478_C15									straight connection		
J1478_C16	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-14	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	22:52	23:11	2L fluid for bio	1800	
J1478_C17	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	7:05	7:22	2L fluid for bio	1800	
J1478_SF18	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	1:49	2:33	Sterivex	2000	
J1478_SF19	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	4:27	5:06	Sterivex	2000	
J1478_SF20	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	6:22	6:56	Sterivex	2000	
J1478_SF 21	deep seawater 3600 m	2022-12-14	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659			Sterivex		
J1478_Cu 22	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-14	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	23:28	23:49	Copper	2000	
J1478_Cu 23	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-14	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	23:58	0:18	Copper	2000	
J1478_Cu 24	1492 / Blue Moon	2022-12-15	15.70957	147.1766	41.5	3659	0:28	0:48	Copper	2000	

KM2214_Huber

Full matrix of incubations

Shipboard SIP-NanoSIMS:

For 1 ATM experiments J2-1471 - South Chamorro Seamount

LV17 pH 9.91

LV16 pH 9.90

Sampling days: 11/29, 12/1, 12/5

Condition	13C	2H	Metabolism	Reps	Time	Temp	pH of replicate C
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	10	9.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	10	9.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	10	9.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	10	9.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	10	9.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	30	9.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	30	9.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	30	9.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	30	9.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	30	9.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	55	9.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	55	9.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	55	9.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	55	9.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	55	9.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	10	9.5-10
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	10	9.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	10	9.5-10
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	10	9.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	10	9.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	30	9.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	30	9-9.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	30	9-9.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	30	9
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	30	9-9.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	55	9-9.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	55	8.5-9
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	55	8.5-9
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	55	8.5-9
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	55	8.5-9
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	10	9.5-10
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	10	9.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	10	9.5-10

4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	10	8.5-9
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	10	9.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	30	9.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	30	9-9.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	30	9.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	30	8.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	30	9-9.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	55	9-9.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	55	8.5-9
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	55	8.5-9
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	55	8
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	55	8.5

For 1 ATM experiments J2-1472 - South Chamorro Seamount

LV17 pH 12.29, alk 125.52

LV16 pH 12.36, alk 124.90

Condition	13C	2H	Metabolism	Reps	Time	Temp	pH of rep C
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	10	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	10	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	10	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	10	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	10	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	30	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	30	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	30	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	30	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	30	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	55	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	55	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	55	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	55	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	55	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	10	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	10	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	10	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	10	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	10	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	30	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	30	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	30	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	30	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	30	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	55	12.5

2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	55	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	55	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	55	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	55	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	10	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	10	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	10	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	10	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	10	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	30	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	30	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	30	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	30	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	30	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	55	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	55	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	55	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	55	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	55	12.5

For 1 ATM experiments J2-1475 - Big Blue

LV (CHEM) 7 pH 12.37

LV15 pH 12.39

LV16 pH 12.34

LV17 pH 12.47

Condition	13C	2H	Metabolism	Reps	Time	Temp	pH of rep C
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	10	12.5 - 13
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	10	12.5 - 13
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	10	12.5 - 13
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	10	12.5 - 13
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	10	12.5 - 13
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	30	12.5 - 13
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	30	12.5 - 13
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	30	12.5 - 13
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	30	12.5 - 13
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	30	12.5 - 13
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	55	12.5 - 13
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	55	12.5 - 13
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	55	12.5 - 13
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	55	12.5 - 13
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	55	12.5 - 13
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	10	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	10	12.5

3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	10	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	10	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	10	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	30	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	30	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	30	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	30	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	30	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	55	12.5
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	55	12.5
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	55	12.5
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	55	12.5
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	55	12.5
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	10	
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	10	
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	10	
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	10	
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	10	
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	30	
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	30	
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	30	
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	30	
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	30	
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	55	
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	55	
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	55	
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	55	
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	55	

For 1 ATM experiments J2-1477 - Big Blue

LV 13

LV 16

LV 17

Condition	13C	2H	Metabolism	Reps	Time	Temp	pH of rep C
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	10	
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	10	
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	10	
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	10	
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	10	
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	30	
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	30	
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	30	

4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	30
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	30
1	None	Water	Control	3	12 hr	55
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	12 hr	55
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	55
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	12 hr	55
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	12 hr	55
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	10
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	10
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	10
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	10
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	10
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	30
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	30
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	30
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	30
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	30
1	None	Water	Control	3	2 day	55
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	2 day	55
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	55
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	2 day	55
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	2 day	55
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	10
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	10
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	10
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	10
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	10
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	30
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	30
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	30
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	30
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	30
1	None	Water	Control	3	6 day	55
2H	Formate	Water	Methanogenesis/Fermentation	3	6 day	55
3	Methanol	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	55
4H	Bicarb	Water	Methanogenesis	3	6 day	55
5	Methane	Water	AOM	3	6 day	55

SIP-NanoSIMS at in-situ pressure (IGTS experiments with Jeff Seewald)

J2-1471 South Chamorro Seamount

J2_1471_IGT5_HiP_Hydrogen exp

Description of experiment: In situ pressure was 4800 psi. During sampling and injection, we tried to maintain that pressure. To this

	Time	Date	Time elapsed (h)	pH	Pressure (psi)	H2 (mmol/L)	CH4 (mmol/L)	Ratio H2:CH4 *100	Alkalinity (meq/L)	Depth (m)
Starting time	5:00 PM	11/30/2022	0	12.12 (pH probe)	4800		25.7	0		2926
T1 - fluid	2:00 PM	12/1/2022	21.3	No pH measured	5300	1.58	25.1	6.294821		
T2 - chemistry and gases	2:00 PM	12/2/2022	46	12 (pH paper)	4700	1.49	25.6	5.820313		
T3 - fluid	1:30 PM	12/3/2022	68.5	12.5 (pH paper)	4505	1.42	24.5	5.795918		
T4 - chemistry and gases	7:00 PM	12/4/2022	98	12.09 (pH probe)	4835	1.45	25	5.8		
T4 - fluid	7:30 PM	12/4/2022	98	12.09 (pH probe)	4835	1.45	25	5.8	109	

J2-1471 South Chamorro Seamount

J2_1471_IGT06_AOM_HiP

Description of experiment: In situ pressure was 4800 psi.. During sampling and injection, we tried to maintain that pressure. To this

	Time	Date	Time elapsed (h)	pH	Pressure (psi)	H2 (mmol/L)	CH4 (mmol/L)	Ratio H2:CH4 *100	Alkalinity	Depth (m)
Starting time	9:45 PM	12/2/2022	0	9.88 (pH probe)	4800		5.02	0		2926
T1 - fluid	11:24 AM	12/3/2022	13.6	9.5 (pH paper)	4500	0.007	5.98	0.117057		
T2 - chemistry and gases	7:00 PM	12/5/2022	~69	10 (pH paper)	4520			#DIV/0!		
T3 - fluid	7:30 PM	12/5/2022	~69.5	10 (pH paper)	4520			#DIV/0!		
T4 - chemistry and gases	5:20 PM	12/7/2022	~115	10-11 (pH paper)	4691			#DIV/0!		
T5 - fluid	6:30 PM	12/7/2022	~116	10-11 (pH paper)	4691			#DIV/0!		

J2-1472 South Chamorro Seamount

J2_1472 IGT1_HiP_NanoSIMS

Description of experiment: In situ pressure was 4800 psi. During sampling and injection, we tried to maintain that pressure. To this

	Time	Date	Time elapsed (h)	pH	Pressure (psi)	H2 (mmol/L)	CH4 (mmol/L)	Ratio H2:CH4 * 100	Alkalinity (meq/L)	Depth (m)
Starting time	5:40 PM	12/1/2022	0	11.78	4800		24.7	0	89.1	
T1 - fluid	4:25 PM	12/2/2022	23.1		5115	0.971	22.5	4.315556		
T2 - chemistry and gases	2:25 PM	12/3/2022	45.1			0.942	21.8	4.321101		
T3 - fluid	3:25 PM	12/4/2022	69.8	12 (pH paper)	4816	0.971	22.6	4.29646		
T4 - fluid + chem and gases	7:30 PM	12/7/2022	145.8	11.6 (probe)	4800			#DIV/0!	91.56	2926

J2-1472 South Chamorro Seamount

J2_1472 IGT4_LoP_NanoSIMS

Description of experiment: In situ pressure was 400 psi. This was the "depressurized" IGT. During sampling and injection, we tried

	Time	Date	Time elapsed (h)	pH	Pressure (psi)	H2 (mmol/L)	CH4 (mmol/L)	Ratio H2:CH4 * 100	Alkalinity (meq/L)	Depth (m)
Starting time	7:35 PM	12/1/2022	0	12.12 (probe)	408		26.4	0	116.46	2926
T1 - fluid	7:43 PM	12/2/2022	24.1	No pH tested	413	0.54	25.6	2.109375		
T2 - chemistry and gases	10:00 PM	12/3/2022	48.4			0.522	24.8	2.104839		
T3 - fluid	4:30 PM	12/4/2022	68.7	12.5 (pH paper)	397	0.532	25	2.128		
T5 - fluid + chem and gases	8:50 PM	12/7/2022		12.11 (pH probe)	422			#DIV/0!	117.53	

Shipboard hydrogen experiments

Description of experiment: Serum vials were filled with 100mL LV box fluid. This particular experiment was from LV15

Condition	Time	Date	Time elapsed	pH	H2 (mmol)	CH4 (mmol)	Ratio H2:CH4
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Starting time (T0)	Control		11/24/22	0 h		8.81	0.702	0.964	0.728216
Starting time (T0)	Hydrogen amended		11/24/22	0 h		8.81	11.6	0.669	17.33931
T1	Control		11/25/2022	20 h	--		0.492	0.696	0.706897
T1	Hydrogen amended		11/25/2022	20 h	--		5.9	0.407	14.49631
T2	Control	6:30 PM	11/27/2022	70 h	--		0.398	0.69	0.576812
T2	Hydrogen amended	6:30 PM	11/27/2022	70 h	--		5.94	0.431	13.7819
T3	Control	4:00 PM	11/29/2022	140 h	--		0.297	0.599	0.495826
T3	Hydrogen amended	4:00 PM	11/29/2022	140 h	--		5.58	0.401	13.91521
T4	Control	2:00 PM	12/3/2022	210 h	--		0.209	0.581	0.359725
T4	Hydrogen amended	2:00 PM	12/3/2022	210 h	--		5.36	0.384	13.95833

Terminated experiment

Description of experiment: Serum vials were filled with 100mL LV box fluid. This particular experiment was from LV17 Dive 1471 at

	Condition	Time	Date	Time elapsed	pH	H2 (umol)	CH4 (umol)	Ratio H2:CH4
Starting time (T0)	Control	3:00 PM	11/29/2022	0 h	9.91	0.0041	4.02	0.00102
Starting time (T0)	Hydrogen amended	3:00 PM	11/29/2022	0 h	9.91	6.06	1.95	3.107692
T1	Control	2:00 PM	12/3/2022	71 h	--	0.0245	3.55	0.006901
T1	Hydrogen amended	2:00 PM	12/3/2022	71 h	--	5.88	1.9	3.094737
T2	Control	7:35 PM	12/5/2022	123 h	--	0.0415	3.15	0.013175
T2	Hydrogen amended	7:35 PM	12/5/2022	123 h	--	5.42	1.78	3.044944
T3	Control	11:30 PM	12/8/2022	199 h	--	0.0032	2.74	0.001168
T3	Hydrogen amended	11:30 PM	12/8/2022	199 h	--	5.2	1.62	3.209877

Terminated experiment

Description of experiment: Serum vials were filled with 100mL LV box fluid. This particular experiment was from LV15

	Condition	Time	Date	Time elapsed	pH	H2 (mmol)	CH4 (mmol)	Ratio H2:CH4
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Starting time (T0)	Control	#DIV/0!
Starting time (T0)	Hydrogen amended	#DIV/0!
T1	Control	#DIV/0!
T1	Hydrogen amended	#DIV/0!
T2	Control	#DIV/0!
T2	Hydrogen amended	#DIV/0!
T3	Control	#DIV/0!
T3	Hydrogen amended	#DIV/0!
T4	Control	#DIV/0!
T4	Hydrogen amended	#DIV/0!

Cultures that grew:				
Blue Moon				
Media type	Dive	Date	Temp (C)	Inoculum
Enceladus	J2-1469	11/26/22	30	PC #4
Enceladus	J2-1469	11/26/22,	30	PC #4
Enceladus	J2-1473	12/6/22	55	Fluids
MJYTGL	J2-1469	11/26/22	30	PC #4
Sulfate reduction	J2-1469	11/26/22,	30	PC #4
Sulfate reduction	J2-1469	11/26/22	30	PC #4
Formate	J2-1469	11/26/22	30	PC #4
AOM	J2-1469	11/26/22	30	PC #4
AOM	J2-1469	11/26/22,	30	PC #4
Celestial				
Media type	Dive	Date	Temp (C)	Inoculum
Enceladus	J2-1470	11/28/22	30	PC #6
Sulfate reduction	J2-1470	11/28/22	30	PC #6
AOM	J2-1470	11/28/22	30	PC #6
MJYTGL	J2-1470	11/28/22	30	PC #6
MJYTGL	J2-1470	11/28/22,	30	PC #6
South Chamorro Seamount				
Media type	Dive	Date	Temp (C)	Inoculum
AOM	J2-1471	11/29/22	55	Fluids
Methanol	J2-1472	11/30/22	55	Fluids
Hydrogenotrophic	J2-1471	11/30/2022	30	Fluids
Hydrogenotrophic	J2-1471	11/29/22	55C	Fluids
Sulfate reduction	J2-1472	11/30/22	55C	Fluids
Enceladus	J2-1471	11/29/22	55C	Fluids
Big Blue				
Media type	Dive	Date	Temp (C)	Inoculum
Sulfate Reduction	J2-1474	12/8/22	30	PC #NG8
AOM	J2-1474	12/8/22	30	PC #NG8
Formate	J2-1474	12/8/22	30	PC #NG8

Media matrix:

Media name	Metabolis	headspac	headspace to add	pH	Tape color	Volume	Volume	# tubes or	Vitamins	2% Na2S	2% Cys-	10%	0.05% methanol (conc.	Incub	Incub	Incuba
Mnat	H2/CO2	H2/CO2	H2/CO2	9.5	pink	30 mL	3 mL	36 vials	2.8 mL -	2.1 mL	none	none	none	10 C	30 C	55 C
Mnat + formate	Formate	N2/CO2	N2/CO2	9.5	white	30 mL	3 mL	36 vials	2.8 mL -	2.1 mL	none	1.22 mL -	none	10 C	30 C	55 C
Ken Takai's MJYTGL	heterotrop	N2	None needed	10.5	red	6 mL	1 mL	36 x 6 mL	none	none	none	none	none	10 C	30 C	55 C
DSM 282 - Our lab's	H2/CO2	H2/CO2	H2/CO2	9.8	blue	7 mL	1 mL	36 x 7 mL	none -	0.075 mL	0.075 mL	none	none	10 C	30 C	55 C
DSM 282 - Our lab's	Formate	N2/CO2	N2/CO2	9.8	green	7 mL	1 mL	36 x 7 mL	none -	0.075 mL	0.075 mL	0.28 mL -	none	10 C	30 C	55 C
DSM 282 - Our lab's	Methanol	N2/CO2	N2/CO2	9.8	yellow	7 mL	1 mL	36 x 7 mL	none -	0.075 mL	0.075 mL	none	0.1 mL - already added	10 C	30 C	55 C
Sulfate reducer	Sulfate	H2/CO2	None needed	10.5	orange	7 mL	1 mL	36 x 7 mL	none -	0.03 mL	none	none	none	10 C	30 C	55 C
Sulfate reducer	AOM	gas with	CH4	10.5	white with	7 mL	1 mL	36 x 7 mL	none -	0.03 mL	none	none	none	10 C	30 C	55 C
Enceladus Medium	Enceladus	H2/CO2	H2/CO2	10.5	white with	7 mL	1 mL	36 x 7 mL	0.063 mL -	0.15 mL	none	none	none	10 C	30 C	55 C
vol additions required									203.87	166.86	8.1 mL	54 mL	3.6 mL			
Already added in lab before																
To add at sea																